

Supplementary Materials for: “Supply-Side Innovations to Increase Equitable Access to Digital Financial Services: Experimental Evidence from Mozambique

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August 3, 2025

1 Supplementary Figures

Figure B1: Number of New Female M-Pesa Clients per Week by TSR Gender

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Figure B2: Number of New Rural Female M-Pesa Clients per Week by TSR Gender

2 Supplementary Tables

Table B1: TSR Hiring Process

	Standard Vodacom TSRs	M4A TSRs
Identification and Screening Process	Subcontractor	Subcontractor
Training Length/Content	One week	One week
Qualification Process	Exam, top scorers hired	Exam, equal number of top female and male scorers hired
Gender Breakdown of Hires	10 percent female	50 percent female

Table B2: TSR Selling Procedure

	Standard Vodacom TSRs	M4A TSRs
Location	No assigned markets, skewed urban	Assigned markets, rural and peri-urban
TSR Demographics	10 percent female	50 percent female
Selling process	SIM card sale, no active registration of M-Pesa	SIM card sale, active push to register M-Pesa
Instruction on M-Pesa setup/use?	No	Yes
Support with first M-Pesa transaction?	No	Yes

3 Additional Robustness Checks

Given the small number of teams that were randomized across markets and that individual teams may be repeatedly assigned to markets, we recognize that there may be less true variation in our data and that our findings may be explained by factors other than the randomized gender composition of the team. To address these concerns, we conduct a randomization inference exercise in which we simulate 500 permutations of TSR team assignment by gender across markets on each market day and estimate the impact of each permuted assignment on our main outcomes of interest. Results from this exercise are presented in [Table B3](#) and suggest that our main findings may be robust to this standard error correction to account for the limited number of teams that are randomly assigned.

[Table B4](#), presents additional results from a comparison of our findings for our main outcomes under alternate model assumptions. Our inferences from our primary specifications do not significantly change when we cluster standard errors by market. In addition, our findings are robust to conducting a stepwise bootstrapped multiple hypothesis testing (MHT) correction that controls for the family-wise error rate (FWER) across outcomes and also accounts for the joint dependence structure of the test statistics ([Romano and Wolf, 2005a,b](#)). We implement this approach, which corrects for false discovery rates under multiple outcomes and multiple treatments, to account for the fact that our outcomes (and their corresponding p-values when we test them) are likely to be on the same causal path and therefore be correlated.¹ We prefer the [Romano and Wolf \(2005a,b\)](#) adjustment over other MHT corrections (also presented in [Table B4](#)) because this approach calculates adjusted p-values that control for the FWER across all of our outcomes while also allowing for the inclusion of control variables and market fixed effects in our specifications.

Table B3: Robustness Check: Randomization Inference, Market-Day Level

	New SIM Accounts per Market Day	New M-Pesa Accounts per Market Day	M-Pesa Used per Market Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Market Day
female	-4.473 (0.006) [0.002]	-0.775 (0.450) [0.384]	-0.579 (0.498) [0.478]	0.074 (0.040) [0.015]
Observations	345	345	345	345
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

The unit of analysis is the market day. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares models, with randomization inference-generated p-values (500 replications) presented in parentheses and standard heteroskedastic-robust p-values presented in brackets. Covariates in adjusted models include whether the incentive was implemented, market and day of the week fixed effects.

Table B4: Robustness Check: Multiple Hypothesis Testing, Market-Day Level

	New SIM Accounts per Market Day	New M-Pesa Accounts per Market Day	M-Pesa Used per Market Day	M-Pesa Conversion Rate per Market Day
female	-4.473 (0.010) <0.016>	-0.775 (0.373) <0.707>	-0.579 (0.449) <0.449>	0.074 (0.038) <0.048>
Observations	345	345	345	345
Control Mean	19.92	9.71	8.53	0.51
Controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Day of Week FE	✓	✓	✓	✓

The unit of analysis is the market day. All models are estimated using ordinary least squares models, corrected for multiple hypothesis testing using the Romano-Wolf correction in parentheses (500 replications), the Holm correction in angled brackets (500 replications), market-level clustered p-values in vertical brackets, and standard heteroskedastic-robust p-values in square brackets. Covariates in adjusted models include whether the incentive was implemented, market and day of the week fixed effects.

References

- Romano, J. P. and Wolf, M. (2005a). Exact and Approximate Stepdown Methods for Multiple Hypothesis Testing. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 100(469):94–108. Publisher: Taylor & Francis _eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1198/016214504000000539>. (Cited on page 4.)
- Romano, J. P. and Wolf, M. (2005b). Stepwise Multiple Testing as Formalized Data Snooping. *Econometrica*, 73(4):1237–1282. _eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/j.1468-0262.2005.00615.x>. (Cited on page 4.)